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ISSUES IN CONDUCTING A SPORADIC LAND REGISTRY CORRECTIVE PROCEDURE IN THE REPUBLIC OF CROATIA ***

Abstract: *The concept of a sporadic corrective procedure, stipulated in the Croatian Land Registry Act, serves as a tool for correcting irregularities in the land registry entries. The purpose of this legal institute is accomplished in situations where the regular procedure does not ensure a proper entry into land registry because, for various reasons, it is not possible to obtain an intabulation clause (clausula intabulandi or title deed) either from the registered owner or from his/her legal successors. The concept of a sporadic corrective procedure had been incorporated into the Croatian legal system before the adoption of the latest Land Registry Act but it was regulated in a single article. The new regulation enables a more extensive application of this institute in judicial practice. Therefore, this paper sheds light on particular open questions related to the implementation of sporadic (individual) land registry corrective procedure. These include the issue of protecting the holder of the right to real estate which has to be registered, the issue of a justifiable reason for initiating a sporadic corrective procedure, and the issue of identifying the persons who has legal interest to initiate a sporadic corrective procedure. Another open question is which deeds or documents for the transfer and establishment of ownership rights may serve*

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as evidence in a sporadic corrective procedure. Another specific issue refers to the envisaged possibility that the court adjudication in these proceedings may be based on equity. In the Croatian judicial practice, there is a dilemma regarding the possibility of proving the acquisition of the ownership right in the sporadic corrective procedure on the basis of usucapio (acquisitive prescription, adverse possession). Hence, the paper attempts to provide guidelines for the regulation of these issues de lege ferenda in a way that would accommodate the general, legal policy and private interests of the holders of ownership rights.

Keywords: *land registry, sporadic corrective procedure, entry, ownership, usucapio (acquisitive prescription, adverse possession).*

1. Introduction

Consolidated land registries have always been a prerequisite and a driver of economic growth, as well as an indicator of the level of a society organization. However, the issue of land registration was neglected for quite a long time, particularly at the time when the Croatian legal system had plenty of socialistic features (Gavella *et al.*, 2007: 13). In the 1960s, when social ownership was the dominant type of ownership, the courts held that a written agreement was a valid instrument for the transfer of ownership in real estate. In the 1980s, which were marked by the construction of large apartment blocks, the so-called “solidarity apartments”, the beneficiaries were only required to fill out the agreement template and pay for the apartment, whereas the slots for entering the cadastral plot number and municipality remained blank. Such practices led to a great discrepancy between a land registry entry and the actual situation (Ružička, 2010: 84, 85). It did not change much after the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Croatia (1990)¹ and reintegration of the Croatian legal system into continental law.² Notably, there was still no major progress after the adoption of the Act on Ownership and Other Proprietary Rights³ and the Land Registry Act⁴ in

¹ Constitution of the Republic of Croatia, *Official Gazette* no. 56/90, 135/97, 08/98, 113/00, 124/00, 28/01, 41/01, 55/01, 76/10, 85/10, 05/14, hereinafter: Constitution.

² The new Croatian Constitution abolished the old dualism in the regulation of ownership, i.e. social ownership was discarded in favour of private ownership (Gavella *et al.*, 2007: 14).

³ Act on Ownership and Other Proprietary Rights, *Official Gazette* no. 91/1996, 68/1998, 137/1999, 22/2000, 73/2000, 114/2001, 79/2006, 141/2006, 146/2008, 38/2009, 153/2009, 90/2010, 143/2012, 152/2014, 81/15, 94/17, 52/25, hereinafter: the OOPR Act.

⁴ Land Registry Act, *Official Gazette* no. 91/96., 68/98., 137/99., 114/01., 100/04., 107/07., 152/08., 126/10, 55/13., 60/13., 108/2017, hereinafter: the LRA-1996.

1996.⁵ In fact, land registries are unconsolidated due to insufficient registration of legal transactions on succession and acquisition related to real property transfers. Agreements on the partition of property among family members, gifts and assignments in inheritance proceedings did not use to be registered in land registries, which resulted in outdated entries or, more precisely, registration of owners who were no longer alive and whose successors could not be reached (Kačer, Rahan, 2023: 223, 224).

Consequently, the purpose and legal goal of the concept of sporadic corrective procedure refer to the harmonization of land registry entries with the actual situation (Golub, 2023: 14). Thus, the latest Land Registry Act (2019) stipulates that a sporadic corrective procedure is a special land registry procedure for correcting land registry entries, conducted when there is a justifiable reason. This procedure may be conducted with regards to one or several land registry files.⁶

The concept of sporadic corrective procedures had been used prior to the adoption of the LRA-1996. However, that period was characterized by the fragmentariness of judicial practice. For example, in northwestern and central Croatia, a sporadic corrective procedure was often applied for land registry consolidation, which was not the case in southern Croatia (Bulka, 2020: 379, 380). The reason why a sporadic corrective procedure was not utilized for the harmonization of land registry files with the actual situation relates to the inadequate regulation of that tool. More precisely, the LRA-1996 normatively regulated a sporadic corrective procedure in only one article.⁷ Detailed formulation of that instrument can be found in the Regulation on the Internal Organization, Maintenance of Land Registries and Performance of Other Tasks in the Land Registry Departments of Courts⁸ (Bulka, 2020: 380).

The legislator has nevertheless identified a sporadic corrective procedure as a chance to efficiently consolidate land registries and accordingly, the LRA-19 regulates that tool in a much more comprehensive fashion (Jurin Bakotić, Paić, Martinović, 2017: 65). Namely, Articles 208-216 of the LRA-2019 set

⁵ The OOPR Act and the LRA-1996 became effective on 1 January 1997.

⁶ Article 208 paragraph 1 of the Land Registry Act, *Official Gazette* no. 63/19, 128/22, 155/23, 127/24., hereinafter: LRA-2019.

⁷ Article 200 of the LRA-1996.

⁸ Regulation on the Internal Organization, Maintenance of Land Registries and Performance of other tasks in the Land Registry Departments of Courts, *Official Gazette* no. 81/1997, 109/2002, 153/2002, 123/2002, 14/2005, 60/2010, 60/2010, 55/2013, 63/2019, 128/2022, 127/2024, hereinafter: Regulation.

forth the requirements and course of a sporadic corrective procedure.⁹

By its nature, a sporadic corrective procedure falls into non-contentious procedures. It should be noted that, since 2023, the Republic of Croatia has been using a universal non-contentious procedure laid down in the Non-Contentious Procedure Act (hereinafter: the NCPA).¹⁰ The provisions of the Civil Procedure Act shall apply to the issues which are not regulated by the NCPA.¹² In that sense, a sporadic corrective procedure is primarily subject to the provisions of the LRA-2019 and the NCPA. In case those two acts are insufficient, the provisions of the Civil Procedure Act shall apply (Kačer, Rahan, 2023: 226).

A sporadic corrective procedure is regarded as a non-contentious procedure; in other words, it shall be applied when there are no conflicting or mutually exclusive interests.¹³ Yet, in reality, the interests of the parties in a sporadic corrective procedure are frequently conflicting. Indeed, the rights of two parties to the same property might often collide. The legislator has envisaged such a possibility by providing the right to submit applications and appeals (objections) which are then tackled by the court and settled in a judicial decision. Moreover, the legislator provides the unsuccessful party with the right to submit an application for correction of the judicial decision (Golub, 2008: 563).¹⁴

This paper analyses the legal requirements for opening and conducting a sporadic corrective procedure. The paper explores is the efficiency of the legal regulation on a sporadic corrective procedure, which should enable

⁹ The Regulation provides guidelines how to conduct a sporadic corrective procedure in Articles 108-114.

¹⁰ Non-Contentious Procedure Act, *Official Gazette* no. 59/23.

¹¹ Until the NCPA was adopted, Croatian courts had adjudicated according to the provisions of the former Non-Contentious Procedure Act, the provisions of the 1934 Introductory Act to the Non-Contentious Judicial Procedure Act, and the provisions of the Act on the Manner of Application of the Legal Rules adopted prior to 6 April 1941 (Golub, 2014: 25).

¹² Article 2 of the NCPA.

¹³ Pursuant to the theory on disputes and conflicts, and the theory on parties in court proceedings, the difference between a civil and non-contentious procedure is based on possible existence of a dispute. More precisely, the cases involving a dispute are dealt with in a civil procedure whereas those lacking it are handled within the framework of a non-contentious procedure. Also, a civil procedure entails conflicting interests while a non-contentious procedure implies parallel and mutually non-exclusive interests (Triva, Belajec, Dika, 2004: 53).

¹⁴ Article 209 paragraphs 6 and 7, Article 210 paragraph 3, Article 211 paragraph 1 and Article 213 paragraph 2 of the LRA-2019.

courts to administer justice in line with equity. It also elaborates the possibility of the court to establish whether ownership rights are acquired on the ground of *usucapio* (acquisitive prescription, adverse possession) principle. These open issues are a challenge both for legal literature and judicial practice. In this regard, the paper offers some solutions which could facilitate the accomplishment of the purpose of a sporadic corrective procedure, which is the harmonization of land registry files with the actual situation as well as the protection of the interests of holders of ownership rights.

2. The reason for opening a sporadic corrective procedure

As highlighted above, the prior poor condition of Croatian land registries could be depicted by files that did not reflect the actual situation due to a failure to register ownership rights and transfers. Therefore, land registry entries were corrected in both regular and special procedures. The parties opted for a special procedure if they had an imperfect title deed. A sporadic corrective procedure falls into special land registry procedures (Đojinčević, 2024: 421).¹⁵ In that sense, there is a justifiable reason for opening a sporadic corrective procedure if a deed or document suggests that a person should be entitled to a right which should have been entered in the land registry and thus implies entry correction, provided that such a right is comprised in the LRA-2019.¹⁶ Generally, it can be said that there is a justifiable reason for conducting a sporadic corrective procedure whenever it comes to incompatibility of a land registry file with the actual situation (Bulka, 2020: 379, 383).

Yet, at this point, one should warn about the inconsistency between the LRA-2019 and the Regulation in terms of the existence of a justifiable reason for conducting a sporadic corrective procedure. Indeed, the Regulation prescribes that a reason for opening a sporadic corrective procedure shall be found justifiable if a deed or document suggests that a person should be entitled to a right which should have been entered in the land registry and thus implies entry correction, provided that such a right is comprised by the LRA-19.¹⁷ In other words, the Regulation requires that a sporadic corrective pro-

¹⁵ Beside a sporadic corrective procedure, the LRA-2019 lays down other special land registry procedures such as land registry establishment and renewal, opening of a land registry and corrective procedure, land registry supplementation, sporadic land registry transformation, linking of a land registry with the registry of deposited contracts and entry of apartment ownerships. Special land registry procedures ensure the validity, up-to-dateness and completeness of data in land registries (Pichler, 2022: 132-144).

¹⁶ Article 208 paragraph 3 of the LRA-2019.

¹⁷ Article 108 paragraph 2 of the Regulation.

cedure shall be supported with a public or notarial document. Since the LRA-2019 does not explicitly define that opening of a sporadic corrective procedure requires a public or notarial document, it can be concluded that a private document would suffice in that context too.¹⁸ Although a legislative act generally prevails over a regulatory act, the Croatian judicial practice (case-law) holds that a private document shall not be a sufficient proof in a sporadic corrective procedure if it is presented as the only proof (Bulka, 2020: 379, 384).¹⁹ It can be asserted that the legislator has opted for regulated rules of assessment of evidence when deciding on possible existence of a justifiable reason for opening a sporadic corrective procedure.²⁰ In fact, regarding the above Act and Regulation, the presence of a justifiable reason for conducting a sporadic corrective procedure cannot be demonstrated only by using deeds or documents, which excludes any other means. Moreover, the legislator has also specified the types of documents which can serve as means for proving the justifiability of a sporadic corrective procedure, i.e. the documents which support the merits of the submitted application (proposal)²¹ (Golub, 2008: 563). It should be stressed that the list of the documents laid down in Article 209 § 4 of the LRA-19, which are depicted as eligible for initiating a sporadic corrective procedure, is illustrative and non-exhaustive, which is a common interpretation mistake. Hence, other documents, if they suggest that a person should be entitled to a right which should have been entered in the land registry, which then implies entry cor-

¹⁸ E.g., a purchase agreement on which the seller's signature is not notarized (Bulka, 2020: 384).

¹⁹ As part of a sporadic corrective procedure, Croatian courts take into account private documents on which the signatures are not notarized, but never as the only evidence in the case (Šago, 2018: 581).

²⁰ In terms of the legal assessment of evidence, legal standards define the requirements for selection, provision and evaluation of evidence. On such an occasion, the judge's position is irrelevant. What matters are the legal requirements for application of the legal rules on establishing the accuracy of the facts. The court is obliged to recognize only those means of proof whose use is permitted by the law. Unlike the said principle, the principle of free assessment of evidence provides the judge with absolute discretion in deciding which evidence will be taken into consideration. When evaluating evidence, the judge is not bound by any legal rule (Triva, 1978: 122, 123).

²¹ For instance, Article 209 § 4 of the LRA-2019 stipulates that a proposal for initiating a sporadic corrective procedure shall incorporate documents that substantiate its justifiability, i.e. documents that support the merits of the proposal (e.g. applicant's documents on the transfer and establishment of ownership rights, which do not meet the requirements for intabulation clause validity, extracts from real property cadastres, notarized statements of real property owners and their successors, which confirm the applicant's ownership rights, etc.).

rection, may serve as a reason for opening a sporadic corrective procedure.²²

The applicant is supposed to demonstrate a certain level of certainty of the presence of circumstances indicating possession of property.²³ More precisely, a justifiable reason for opening a sporadic corrective procedure implies a high probability that a person is entitled to the right to property.²⁴ On the other hand, the existence of ownership rights does not have to be absolutely certain.²⁵ If the court insisted on the certainty of the existence of ownership rights, a sporadic corrective procedure would not be necessary since, in such a case, the court would not have any other assignment except to confirm the existence of ownership rights (Golub, 2008: 561, 562).

3. Decision-making according to equity

The decision-making related to the hearings, applications and appeals (objections) in a sporadic corrective procedure is subject to the referring provisions of the LRA-2019.^{26,27} Namely, the court is bound to enable all the

²² The applicant's documents on the transfer and establishment of ownership rights which do not meet the requirements for intabulation clause validity are all those documents that cannot be executed in a regular, fully formal land registry procedure, particularly those that do not meet the requirements on former real property owners (predecessors). A sporadic corrective procedure can also be initiated on the basis of documents containing erroneously registered real property based on a legal transaction, which is not permitted in a regular land registry procedure. The applicants shall supplement their proposals with a description of the respective legal transaction and indicate that there was an omission when preparing the legal transaction. In many cases, the testator's assets are distributed among his/her successors based on a 20-year-old order establishing succession, which contains only descriptions and common names of items but not land registration codes which are required for execution of such an order in the land registry. Such an order can be neither corrected nor amended in inheritance proceedings since the court made no mistake when preparing it and the only way to execute it is within the framework of a sporadic corrective procedure (Kačer, Rahan, 2023: 231-234).

²³ A court's certificate attesting the existence of a circumstance, accompanied with the level of its certainty, indicates that the court has established that there are more proofs supporting the existence of a relevant fact than those denying it (Triva, 1978: 377).

²⁴ Article 208 § 3 of the LRA-2019.

²⁵ If the court's certificate excludes any reasonable doubt about the validity and authenticity of a fact, it shall be deemed that a certain thesis has been fully proven, i.e. that a certain fact is very likely to exist (Triva, 1978:377)..

²⁶ Provisions of Articles 202 and 203 of the LRA-2019 and Article 216 § 5 of the LRA-2019.

²⁷ Land registry procedures include both a corrective procedure which refers to a cadastral municipality (exceptionally, to a part of a cadastral municipality) and a corrective procedure

attendants of a hearing to make observations on other people's applications and appeals (objections), and to accompany their assertions with evidence which can be presented right away because the decision-making related to the applications and appeals (objections) primarily rests on agreements of the parties and other stakeholders; thus, the court is obliged to provide all the attendants with the possibility to reach such agreements, which are then entered in the minutes. In regard to the registration of applications and appeals (objections) in the title deed and encumbrance sheet, the court shall, if possible, deliver a respective decision based on reached agreements if they are permitted and implementable. In case no agreement has been reached, the court shall adjudicate on the basis of the equity principle.²⁸ Adjudication based on the principle of equity entails the judge's discretionary right to flexibly apply a general legal standard to the parties who are deemed equal in the referring judicial proceedings (Kačer, Rahan, 2023: 236).²⁹

At this point, it should be noted that such a possibility is considerably restricted in a sporadic corrective procedure.³⁰ In fact, in the event that the applicant bases his/her proposal for entry correction on a public or private document which implies the existence of the ownership rights that are supposed to be entered in a land registry file, but the respondent opposes such a proposal, the court shall apply substantive law standards or, in other words, act pursuant to the principle of legality. If the court decides in line

which refers to a particular land registry file (Golub, 2014: 24).

²⁸ The principle of equity (lat. *aequitas*) serves to make law as fair as possible. In some cases, a legal standard cannot regulate a legal relation in the fairest way. Thus, when applying a legal standard in some cases, a legal standard should be adapted to the principle of equity. Roman jurists believed that traces of equity postulates can be found in society, not only in the Roman one but also in other communities (*ius gentium*), as well as in deep-rooted customs, beliefs and views (Romic, 1989: 24).

²⁹ As a legal category, the principle of equity is a complex concept which primarily refers to equal treatment of parties, but also to logical, economically justified, moral and politically necessary action. In the event of an equity-based trial, decision-making based on equity implies a deviation from strict application of substantive rules since such application would be contrary to the general perception of justice and equity (Tamaš, 2009: 4).

³⁰ It is beyond any doubt that the development of legal transactions entails the need for application of general provisions and flexible legal rules and standards, i.e. norms imposing a general rule which can be interpreted differently in every particular case. Hence, courts are enabled to adapt a general standard to a concrete case and thus resolve the conflict in a fair way and in compliance with the law. However, one should be aware of the fact that such an approach, though necessary, may be abused and can imply negative consequences. Moreover, it may result in legal insecurity, particularly if courts exceed the powers conferred thereon and start to perform the legislative function (Osrečak, 2014: 54).

with the principle of equity and contrary to provisions of substantive law (*contra legem*) or beyond them (*praeter legem*), the respective judicial decision shall be illegal. Hence, the parties whose applications and appeals (objections) have been upheld neither entirely nor partly, as well as the parties whose entry or order of entry has been amended, supplemented or deleted, shall be entitled to submit an application for correction of the judicial decision,³¹ which would result in the derogation of the competent land register court's decision made on the basis of the principle of equity (Golub, 2023: 17).

4. Proving the acquisition of ownership rights through usucapio (acquisitive prescription, adverse possession)

In order to ensure the principle of security in legal transactions and everyday life, there is often the need to harmonize the actual possession of real property or land with its legal status, and thus eliminate the respective discrepancy in public registries (land registries and cadastres) and transform the actual possession into a subjective right (Jakelić, 2024: 437).

Both in the Croatian legal literature and judicial practice, one can often hear the question whether the court can acknowledge, within the framework of a sporadic corrective procedure, the acquisition of ownership rights through *usucapio* (acquisitive prescription, adverse possession). More precisely, it is obvious that the parties face numerous obstacles from the area of procedural and substantive law when they initiate proceedings in which ownership rights are to be demonstrated on the basis of a declaratory action. For example, the parties frequently experience hardship when they seek the successors of the registered owners of real property. On such an occasion, they are forced to submit actions and applications through diplomatic channels and appoint temporary attorneys. Such procedures are expensive and long-lasting (Kačer, Rahan, 2023: 224). For that reason, the public concerned perceives a sporadic corrective procedure as an alternative to a civil procedure. Yet, simplified administration of justice in this non-contentious procedure may result in violation of registered ownership rights.

Furthermore, a decision on the opening of a sporadic corrective procedure has an informative character, meaning that irregular service does not pre-

³¹ The court shall instruct those whose applications or appeals have been upheld neither entirely nor partially, as well as those whose entry or order of entry in the land registry has been amended, supplemented or deleted, to exercise their right to appeal in a civil procedure by means of an application for correction of the judicial decision (Article 203 § 5 of the LRA-2019).

vent further judicial action.³²³³ Consequently, it may happen that the registered owner of real property or land has not even been informed about an opened sporadic corrective procedure (Kačer, Rahan, 2023: 225).³⁴³⁵ The principle of orality, as a working method in court proceedings, and the right to be heard are not so important in a non-contentious procedure as they are in a civil procedure.³⁶

In the Croatian judicial practice, there is a case in which the applicants based their application (proposal) for opening and conducting a sporadic corrective procedure on the assertion that they had obtained the ownership of real property by means of *usucapio* (acquisitive prescription, adverse possession). The applicants enclosed no document with the application, but they proposed a hearing of witnesses and an on-site inspection. The Municipal Court in Split dismissed the application. The applicant submitted an appeal against that judicial decision, but the County Court in Varaždin rejected the appeal and provided the explanation that the first instance court dismissed the application due to the fact that, in a sporadic corrective procedure, there

³² Article 212 § 2 of the LRA-2019.

³³ A decision on opening a sporadic corrective procedure encompasses a notice which shall be promptly published *ex officio* by the court. The notice invites all the people who contest the correction of the land registry file and who hold that the land registry file should be supplemented, amended or additionally corrected, to submit their application and appeals (objections) to the court within a specified deadline. If there are no applications or appeals (objections), and the file and land registries suggest that the application or proposal is well-founded, the court can make a respective decision without a hearing. Applications or objections can be submitted within 30 days after publishing of the notice on the e-Notice Board. The notice shall be published on the e-Notice Board, the notice boards of the court, competent cadastral office, local self-government unit or in any other appropriate way at the expense of the applicant (Article 211 §§ 1 – 3 of the LRA-2019).

³⁴ Since the legislator has prescribed that an application (proposal) for opening a sporadic corrective procedure does not have to include the people who are supposed to be eliminated from the land registry file (respondents), it is clear that the purpose of such regulation refers to acceleration of the procedure and the possibility to conduct a sporadic corrective procedure even if the respondents are unknown, i.e. their residence is unknown. For instance, some land registry entries are more than 100 years old and it is likely that the registered owners are not only out of reach but also deceased (Bulka, 2020: 386).

³⁵ Hence, the registered owner of real property or land may be deleted from a land registry file, which can affect legal security, the guarantee of the right to property and the right to a fair trial (Bulka, Dešić, 2025: 269).

³⁶ During a hearing or decision-making based on written statements, the court, in a non-contentious procedure, does not have to check what other stakeholders think about every allegation or proposal (Zuglia, 1956: 38).

shall be no establishment of facts related to the acquisition of ownership rights through *usucapio* (acquisitive prescription, adverse possession) and that the applicant did not base his application on the documents that would surely indicate that he had the ownership rights which were not registered with the competent land registry but on the assertion that he had been in possession of the respective real property for quite a long time.³⁷

However, the case-law also involves a ruling of the County Court in Varaždin,³⁸ revealing a completely different opinion on the same legal matter: “the position of the first-instance court that the facts related to *usucapio* cannot be processed in a land registry procedure but only in a civil procedure is wrong. Considering that the applicant, in the light of a sporadic corrective procedure, disposed of all means of proof, including witness testimonies, the first-instance court should have taken all presented evidences and established the facts which can support the merits of the application (proposal)” (Bulka, Dešić, 2025: 275, 276). For all those reasons, the applicant lodged an application for admission of judicial review.³⁹ The Supreme Court of the

³⁷ County Court in Varaždin, Gž Zk-694/2021-2 of 10 January 2022, <https://www.iusinfo.hr/sudska-praksa/ZSRH2021VzGzZkB694A2>.

³⁸ County Court in Varaždin, Permanent Office in Koprivnica, no. Gž Zk-214/2019-2 of 27 January 2020, <https://www.iusinfo.hr/sudska-praksa/ZSRH2019GzZkB214A2>.

³⁹ Pursuant to the 2019 and 2022 amendments to the Civil Procedure Act, aimed at new regulation of judicial review which has become a redress used for promotion of the role of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Croatia in ensuring uniform application of law, the decision-making regarding the admissibility of judicial review has been detached from making decisions on its substance. The so-called “second appeal by permission” is the only form of judicial review in a civil procedure in the Republic of Croatia. The Supreme Court of the Republic of Croatia shall permit review if it can encourage a decision on an issue that has been elaborated by lower courts and is highly relevant for reaching a final decision in the dispute, for uniform application of law and corresponding equality for all or for judicial practice development. The Supreme Court shall particularly permit review in the following cases: if the case revolves around a legal matter which has already been elaborated by a second instance court, but its ruling deviates from the judicial practice of the Supreme Court, if the case leans on a legal matter that has not appeared yet in the case-law of the Supreme Court, if the case-law of higher courts is not uniform, if the decisions of the Supreme Court on that matter are not mutually compatible or if the Supreme Court has already adopted a stance and the ruling of the second instance court is based on that stance, but taking account of the reasons presented in the first instance and appellate procedure and of the amendments in the legal system, resulting from new legislation, international treaties, and decisions and rulings of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Croatia, European Court of Human Rights and Court of Justice of the European Union, the case-law should be reviewed (Pichler, Nedić, 2023: 332, 333).

Republic of Croatia⁴⁰ declared the review admissible and provided the following explanation: “the application of S. D. for admission of judicial review of the ruling of the County Court in Varaždin, Permanent Office in Koprivnica, no. Gž Zk-214/2019-2 of 27 January 2020, which confirmed the decision of the Municipal Court in Split, Permanent Office in Supetar, no. Z-4798/2017 of 4 February 2019, is admissible and the admissibility refers to the following question: “Can the acquisition of ownership rights through *usucapio* (acquisitive prescription, adverse possession) be acknowledged in a sporadic corrective procedure and can the applicant demonstrate his/her unregistered ownership by other evidence, except by means of documents, i.e. by witness testimonies, on-site inspection and similar?”⁴¹ After his application had been declared admissible, the applicant submitted an application for judicial review to the Supreme Court of the Republic of Croatia, after which the latter responded in the following way: “In a sporadic corrective procedure, the applicant is not entitled to demonstrate his/her unregistered ownership by other evidence, except by means of documents, i.e. by witness testimonies, on-site inspection and similar.”⁴²

At this point, some conclusions about the opening of a sporadic corrective procedure and on the decision-making after respective application (proposal) submission can already be drawn. A sporadic corrective procedure is divided into two phases.

The first phase relates to the opening of a sporadic corrective procedure.⁴³ It requires a decision on possible verification of a justifiable reason for conducting a sporadic corrective procedure. On that occasion, the court is not supposed to deal with the merits of the application (proposal) and decide on possible correction of a land registry file. Possible existence of the justifiable reason is to be established on the basis of public documents which shall be enclosed with the application (proposal) and on the level of the present certainty. In this phase of the procedure, the application (proposal) shall not be based only on the alleged *usucapio* (acquisitive prescription, adverse possession) and accompanying witness testimonies and on-site inspections. In the

⁴⁰ Hereinafter, SCRC.

⁴¹ SCRC, Revd-2769/2021-2 of 2 September 2021, <https://www.iusinfo.hr/sudska-praksa/VSRH2021RevdB2769A2>.

⁴² SCRC, Rev-346/2023 of 13 June 2023, <https://www.iusinfo.hr/sudska-praksa/VSRH2023RevB346A2>.

⁴³ No appeal against a decision on opening a sporadic corrective procedure is permitted. On the other hand, a decision on dismissing an application for opening a sporadic corrective procedure can be objected (Article 213 §§ 1 and 3 of the LRA-2019).

subsequent phase, the applicant has the burden of proof to demonstrate his/her right to property. In order to state his/her case, he/she can use all the evidence, his/her right to be heard, witness testimonies and on-site inspections. In a non-contentious procedure, the court also has inquisitorial powers and can decide on the taking of evidence (e.g. hearing next-door neighbours)⁴⁴. It can also invite a cadastral official in the capacity of a cadastral data expert and, if necessary, other expert witnesses (Bulka, Dešić, 2025: 277-279).

4.1. The issue of double *lis pendens*

The theory of procedural law reveals the inadmissibility of conducting two judicial proceedings initiated on the basis of one and the same application (proposal) (Triva, 1978: 319). In this regard, Croatian judicial practice had to handle the issue of simultaneously conducted civil procedure aimed at the establishment of ownership rights and a sporadic corrective procedure. In case a civil procedure involving an applicant for a sporadic corrective procedure and a registered owner of real property or land has already been initiated, there could be no justifiable reason for opening and conducting a sporadic corrective procedure since the applicant can by no means have a legal interest in two procedures with the same goal, i.e. ensuring the right to the same property. Thus, the application for a sporadic corrective procedure shall be rejected.⁴⁵

5. Conclusion

The current condition of Croatian land registries justifies the legal purpose of a sporadic corrective procedure, which is harmonization of land registry files with the actual situation (Golub, 2023: 13). However, the public concerned perceives the concept of a sporadic corrective procedure as a tool for handling all inconsistencies in land registries. Such a perception has brought about the old dilemma: does the end justify the means? In this context, this dilemma primarily refers to possible violation of the rights of registered real property owners. Indeed, the purpose of a sporadic corrective procedure cannot be the circumvention of the regular procedure for registration of ownership rights.

⁴⁴ Good judicial policy tends to invite neighbours whose plot of land borders with the cadastral plot concerned to hearings (Bulka, 2020: 392).

⁴⁵ County Court in Varaždin, Gž Zk-694/2021-2 of 10 January 2022 and County Court in Varaždin, Permanent Office in Koprivnica, Gž Zk-633/2022-2 of 27 October 2022, <https://www.iusinfo.hr/sudska-praksa/ZSRH2022VzGzZkB633A2>

This concept has enabled the legislator to efficiently consolidate land registries, eradicate obsolete files and harmonize them with the actual situation. This paper suggests that the legislator's task does not imply smooth implementation.

The uniform case-law results from the discrepancy between the LRA-2019, the Regulation and their interpretation. In principle, an imperfect title deed may serve as a proof that someone should be entitled to unregistered ownership rights. Such a document demonstrating transfer or establishment of ownership rights does not have to be public. Yet, it shall not represent the only evidence in a procedure.

With respect to a sporadic corrective procedure, one of the acute case-law problems refers to the decision-making based on adjudication in line with the equity principle, which is still regarded as an unexplored area (Kačer, Rahan, 2023: 238). Moreover, if a court's decision made on the basis of this principle is illegal, the competent court shall derogate such a decision.

It is important to unambiguously elaborate why *usucapio* (acquisitive prescription, adverse possession) should not be indicated as a ground for the acquisition of ownership rights in a sporadic corrective procedure.⁴⁶ Namely, in order to acknowledge *usucapio*, two requirements shall be cumulatively met: possession in good faith and duration of continuous possession. Therefore, special attention should be paid to the right to be heard, which is not the case in a sporadic corrective procedure since the decision-making in this procedure does not require a hearing.

The conclusions presented in this paper are aimed at encouraging further research and seeking answers to the questions raised in regard to conducting a sporadic corrective procedure. For example, does a sporadic corrective procedure need to be conducted with respect to an entire land registry file, or can it refer to only one of the cadastral plots in a land registry file? When can a regular procedure for amending a land registry file, conducted before a competent cadastral body, replace a sporadic corrective procedure conducted before a land register court? What kind of effect on land registration has the fact that a sporadic corrective procedure has been opened? All in all, the suggestions provided in this paper may serve as guidelines for regulation of these issues *de lege ferenda*. In any case, a possible legislative initiative should be aimed at promoting legal security and protection of individual, property owners' and general interests.

⁴⁶ This is particularly relevant since *usucapio* has been indicated as a ground for the acquisition of ownership rights in 95% of cases involving a hearing and on-site inspection (Bulka, Dešić, 2025: 280).

References

- Bulka Z. (2020). Pojedinačni ispravni postupak u svjetlu novoga Zakona o zemljišnim knjigama. *Zbornik Pravnog fakulteta Sveučilišta u Rijeci*. 41 (1). 379-398.
- Bulka Z., Dešić, J. (2025). Dosjelost u kontekstu pojedinačnog ispravnog postupka – odjeci jedne revizijske odluke Vrhovnog suda Republike Hrvatske. *Zbornik Pravnog fakulteta Sveučilišta u Rijeci*. 46 (1). 261-282.
- Đojinčević J. (2024). *Opravdani razlog za pojedinačni ispravni postupak*. Tradicionalno XXXIX savjetovanje Aktualnosti hrvatskog zakonodavstva i pravne prakse, Godišnjak 31, str. 421-428. Organizator: Zagreb
- Gavella N., Josipović T., Gliha I., Belaj V., Stipković Z. (2007). *Stvarno pravo*. Zagreb: Narodne novine
- Golub A. (2014). Pojedinačni zemljišnoknjižni ispravni postupak – mogućnost usklađivanja zemljišnoknjižnog i stvarnog stanja nekretnina. *Hrvatska pravna revija*. 23-33.
- Golub A. (2023). *Pojedinačni zemljišnoknjižni ispravni postupak – pitanja i dvojbe u sudskoj praksi nakon 25 godina primjene*. Zagreb: Informator. 6803. 13-18.
- Golub A. (2023). *Pojedinačni zemljišnoknjižni ispravni postupak*, Zagreb: Informator. 6802.
- Golub A. (2008). *Utvrđivanje činjenica u pojedinačnom zemljišnoknjižnom ispravnom postupku*. Tradicionalno XXIII savjetovanje Aktualnosti hrvatskog zakonodavstva i pravne prakse. Godišnjak 15. Zagreb: Organizator
- Jakelić D. (2024). *Još nešto o tužbama na utvrđenje prava vlasništva dosjelošću (dileme koje to ni(su))*. Godišnjak 31. Aktualnosti hrvatskog zakonodavstva i pravne prakse. Zagreb: Organizator
- Jurin Bakotić V., Paić I., Martinović M. (2017). Pojedinačno sređivanje nesređenog zemljišnoknjižnog stanja kroz institut pojedinačnog ispravnog postupka. *Elektronički zbornik radova Veleučilišta u Šibeniku*. 11 (3-4). 63-72.
- Kačer B., Rahan D. (2023). *O pojedinačnom zemljišnoknjižnom ispravnom postupku*. Zbornik radova 36. Susreta Kopaoničke škole prirodnog prava Slobodan Perović, Beograd, Tom II. 223-239.
- Osrečak J. (2014). Poredbenopravni prikaz načela savjesnosti i poštenja. *Zagrebačka pravna revija*. 3 (1). 53-77.
- Pichler D. (2022). *Novo zemljišnoknjižno uređenje*. Osijek: Sveučilište Josipa Jurja Strossmayera u Osijeku, Pravni fakultet Osijek

Pichler D., Nedić T. (2023). *Preventing Co-owners From Using Co-owned (Common) Property*. Proceedings of the Tenth International Scientific Conference Social Changes in the Global World. 1(10). 325-336.

Romac A. (1989). *Rječnik rimskog prava*. Zagreb: Informator

Ružička B. (2010). *Zemljišna knjiga. Povezivanje zemljišne knjige i knjige položenih ugovora i upis vlasništva posebnog dijela nekretnine*. Zagreb: Novi informator

Šago D. (2018). Uređivanje zemljišnoknjižnog stanja pojedinačnim ispravnim postupkom. *Zbornik Pravnog fakulteta Sveučilišta u Rijeci*. 39 (1). 575-597.

Tamaš V. (2009). Primena načela pravičnosti u pravnim shvatanjima i odlukama Vrhovnog suda Srbije. *Pravo – teorija i praksa*. 11-12 (26). 3-14.

Triva S., Belajec V., Dika M. (2004). *Građansko parnično procesno pravo*. Zagreb: Narodne novine

Triva S. (1978). *Građansko parnično procesno pravo*. Zagreb: Narodne novine

Zuglia S. (1956). *Vanparnični postupak*. Zagreb: Školska knjiga

Legal sources

Ustav Republike Hrvatske (Constitution of the Republic of Croatia), *Narodne novine*, br. 56/90, 135/97, 08/98, 113/00, 124/00, 28/01, 41/01, 55/01, 76/10, 85/10, 05/14.

Zakon o vlasništvu i drugim stvarnim pravima (Act on Ownership and Other Proprietary Rights), *Narodne novine*, br. 91/1996, 68/1998, 137/1999, 22/2000, 73/2000, 114/2001, 79/2006, 141/2006, 146/2008, 38/2009, 153/2009, 90/2010, 143/2012, 152/2014, 81/15, 94/17, 52/25.

Zakon o zemljišnim knjigama (Land Registry Act), *Narodne novine*, br. 91/96, 68/98, 137/99, 114/01, 100/04, 107/07, 152/08, 126/10, 55/13, 60/13, 108/17.

Zakon o zemljišnim knjigama (Land Registry Act), *Narodne novine*, br. 63/19, 128/22, 155/23, 127/24.

Zakon o izvanparničnom postupku (Non-Contentious Procedure Act), *Narodne novine*, br. 59/23.

Pravilnik o unutarnjem ustroju, vođenju zemljišnih knjiga i obavljanju drugih poslova u zemljišnoknjižnim odjelima sudova (Regulation on the Internal Organization, Maintenance of Land Registries and Performance of

other tasks in the Land Registry Departments of Courts), *Narodne novine*, br. 81/1997, 109/2002, 153/2002, 123/2002, 14/2005, 60/2010, 60/2010, 55/2013, 63/2019, 128/2022, 127/2024.

Case-law

Vrhovni sud Republike Hrvatske (Supreme Court of the Republic of Croatia), Revd-2769/2021-2 of 2 September 2021, <https://www.iusinfo.hr/sudska-praksa/VSRH2021RevdB2769A2>

Vrhovni sud Republike Hrvatske (Supreme Court of the Republic of Croatia), Rev-346/2023 of 13 June 2023, <https://www.iusinfo.hr/sudska-praksa/VSRH2023RevB346A2>

Županijski sud u Varaždinu (County Court in Varaždin), Gž Zk-694/2021-2 of 10 January 2022, <https://www.iusinfo.hr/sudska-praksa/ZSRH2021VzG-zZkB694A2>

Županijski sud u Varaždinu, Stalna služba u Koprivnici (County Court in Varaždin, Permanent Office in Koprivnica), Gž Zk-633/2022-2 of 27 October 2022, <https://www.iusinfo.hr/sudska-praksa/ZSRH2022VzGzZkB633A2>

Županijski sud u Varaždinu, Stalna služba u Koprivnici (County Court in Varaždin, Permanent Office in Koprivnica), Gž Zk-214/2019-2 of 27 January 2020, <https://www.iusinfo.hr/sudska-praksa/ZSRH2019GzZkB214A2>

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ПРОБЛЕМАТИКА СПРОВОЂЕЊА ПОЈЕДИНАЧНОГ ЗЕМЉИШНОКЊИЖНОГ ИСПРАВНОГ ПОСТУПКА У РЕПУБЛИЦИ ХРВАТСКОЈ

Резиме

Институт појединачног исправног поступка у Закону о земљишним књигама, у Републици Хрватској, постоји као средство исправљања неправилности у уписима. Институт појединачног исправног поступка своју сврху остварује у ситуацијама када редовним поступком није могуће спровести земљишнокњижни упис, јер из разних разлога није могуће прибавити клаузулу интабуланди, било од књижног власника, било од његових правних следбеника. У правном поретку Републике Хрватске, институт појединачног исправног поступка постојао је и пре доношења „новог” Закона о земљишним књигама, али био је уређен само једним чланом закона. Ново уређење овог института омогућило је његову екстензивну примену у судској пракси. Због тога, рад ће проблематизовати одређена отворена питања у вези са спровођењем појединачног исправног поступка: питање заштите носиоца права на некретнини у односу на коју се упис права захтева, питање шта се може сматрати оправданим разлогом за покретање појединачног исправног поступка, те ко има правни интерес за покретањем појединачног исправног поступка? Које исправе о преносу или оснивању књижних права могу бити доказ у исправном поступку? Као посебан проблем јавља се могућност да суд у овим поступцима одлучује према правичности. Такође, у судској пракси у Републици Хрватској отворила се дилема у вези с могућношћу да се у појединачном исправном поступку може доказивати аквизиција права власништва одржајем. Због свега наведеног, у раду ће се покушати дати смернице за регулацију ових питања *de lege ferenda* на начин који ће задовољити опште, политичкоправне, али и приватноправне интересе носилаца земљишнокњижних права.

Кључне речи: земљишне књиге, поступак, упис, власништво, одржај.